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**OPEN EARTH
MONITOR**

D2.7 Report "Status and prospect for European environmental data"

Final version

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Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface (API means "Web API" in this document)
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CIFS	Common Internet File System
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DEIMS-SDR	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DMP	Data Management Principles
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
EV	Essential Variable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FTPS	File Transfer Protocol Secured
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GFW	Global Forest Watch
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
JRC	Joint Research Center
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
STAC	Spatio-Temporal Asset Catalogue

Executive summary

This document is the second version of the D2.2 Report "Status and prospect for European environmental data". It extends and adds information related to the European catalogues.

The second part is focused on environmental datasets related to the project use cases and we cited new methodologies for FAIRness assessment.

In the last section, there is a description of the STAC catalogues included in the project. Some of these catalogues are pending completion.

1. European Environmental catalogues

The following subsections update and extend the most significant catalogues explored in the previous deliverable D2.2.

1.1 JRC data catalogue

The <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> is the central catalogue of the Joint Research centre. It consists of 3195 datasets. They consider their data Findable, Accessible and Interoperable. In this catalogue, you can find an inventory of data produced by the JRC in accordance with the JRC Data Policy. In addition to a portal, access to the catalogue through an API is possible with the following API interfaces:

- CKAN action API, RPC-style API that exposes some legacy features to existing API clients.
- ODCAT action API, RPC-style API that it is recommended for new API clients

An open API can be used to access the portal records as documented here: <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/docs/>

1.2 EEA SDI data catalogue

The <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/> is the discovery and access service of the EEA data produced both by EEA staff and from outside (ETCs, contractors, and general public). It is a reference version of geospatial datasets produced, maintained or published by the EEA.

It provides a persistent archiving of the datasets (not altered over time) where datasets are to be versioned – not to be deleted or edited. Data is classified using the INSPIRE themes. A series of thematic metadata portals (which are subsets of the main SDI catalogue following specific thematic requirements) can be accessed through <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/api/sources>.

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Data is stored in a spatial database: PostgreSQL and PostGIS and in a File-based storage system accessible via CIFS (internally) and "Direct download" (DataShare) as well as HTTPS, WebDavS and FTPS (externally). Metadata is stored in a data model called the EEA metadata profile that contains all optional elements offered by ISO 19115 and INSPIRE which are regarded as useful for EEA (https://taskman.eionet.europa.eu/projects/public-docs/wiki/Cataloguemetadata_guidelines)

Additional information here:

https://taskman.eionet.europa.eu/projects/public-docs/wiki/EEA_SD1

The catalogue is based in GeoNetwork 4.0.8.0, so it should also be available by GeoNetwork API, as well as the CSW standard.

<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/csw?request=GetCapabilities&service=CSW>

Figure 1: User interface of EEA SDI catalogue and the entry point to the thematic catalogues

1.3 Copernicus Services

1.3.1 Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service

The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) Catalogue can be found here: <https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/catalogue#/>. It offers search, visualisation and download capabilities. Regarding re-use, it uses the licence model of the CAMS data that can be found here: <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/licences/copernicus/>.

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Catalogue

Reset
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PRODUCT FAMILY ▼

- Annual regional reanalyses
- Anthropogenic emissions
- Climate forcings
- Fire emissions
- Global analyses
- Global forecasts

Global forecasts of aerosol - sulphates #1

This service provides daily global forecasts of aerosol mass mixing ratios up to five days in advance.

Parameter: Sulphates concentration

More details
Data Download

Total results: 263 BETA

Global forecasts of aerosol - black carbon #2

Figure 2: User interface of the CAMS catalogue

1.3.2 Copernicus Marine Service

The Copernicus Marine Data Store <https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products> is a product catalogue that allows to download or to visualise data across nearly 15 variables including hindcast, current and forecast data. It provides 284 products to date. The Findability and Accessibility aspects are covered by it.

Regarding the Reuse of data, the product quality dashboard explores monthly scientific performance and product quality information updates. In it, you will find generic information on the quality of blue ocean parameters, the physical ocean and ocean circulation parameters available in the CMEMS catalogue. The quality of CMEMS products is documented and can be found on the catalogue, along with each product. One major source of deviation is the day-to-day fluctuation in the number of available observations which are used for the elaboration of this product. Hence, recent time series of the daily number of valid observations per parameter are shown to inform on potential quality drops due to this specific source of uncertainty. This information is updated on a daily basis.

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Figure 3: User interface of Copernicus Marine Data Store catalogue and quality dashboard

1.3.3 Copernicus Land Monitoring Service

The previous description in the document D2.2 of this service is obsolete and now there is a new distribution related to the global and other products. The new portal gathers local, European and global datasets in a single access point. It provides geographical information on land cover and its changes, land use, ground motion, vegetation state, water cycle and earth surface energy variables for Europe and global scope.

The current catalogue <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/dataset-catalog> has the following user interface (Figure 4). For each dataset, the user can download either the full dataset or define an area of interest and specific time. This catalogue is linked to the Data Viewer.

Figure 4: User interface CLMS dataset catalogue

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By clicking on the information icon In the Data Viewer table of contents, you will find detailed information about the dataset characteristics, quality, how to access the metadata and related technical documents.

Figure 5: User interface CLMS data viewer

Figure 6: Info of CORINE Land Cover product

In this link <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/how-to-guides> you can find how to access the products.

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1.4 DEIMS-SDR

DEIMS-SDR (Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry) <https://deims.org/> is an information management system powered by the eLTER research infrastructure. It allows discovering long-term ecosystem research sites around the globe, along with the data gathered at those sites and the people and networks associated with them. DEIMS-SDR describes a wide range of sites and provides a wealth of information including each site's location, ecosystems, facilities, parameters measured and research themes. It is also possible to access a growing number of datasets and data products associated with the sites. DEIMS-SDR belongs to the service components of the emerging eLTER Research Infrastructure. While being used as eLTER site registry it also offers services to European peers and the global user communities.

There are four main resource types in DEIMS: Sites, Datasets, Sensors and Activities.

This is essentially a discovery facility. When an asset is found (e.g. a site), access to the data on this site is not directly provided. Only the site itself allows access to the data.

Figure 7: Home page and example of a site page in DEIMS

1.5 GBIF

GBIF —the Global Biodiversity Information Facility— is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth. The GBIF network, working through the participant nodes, provides data-holding institutions around the world with common standards, best practices and open-source tools enabling them to share information about where and when species have been recorded. This knowledge derives from many different kinds of sources, including everything from museum specimens collected in the 18th and 19th century to DNA barcodes and smartphone photos recorded in recent days and weeks.

The portal and API provides easy access to occurrences (observations) and species (taxonomy) datasets (occurrences datasets from organisations integrated in GBIF).

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The GBIF API is a RESTful JSON based API. The base URL for v1 you should use is: <https://api.gbif.org/v1/>. The technical info about how to access the data can be found here: <https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/>

The API is split into logical sections to ease understanding:

Registry: Provides means to create, edit, update and search for information about the datasets, organisations (e.g. data publishers), networks and the means to access them (technical endpoints). The registered content controls what is crawled and indexed in the GBIF data portal, but as a shared API may also be used for other initiatives.

Species: Provides services to discover and access information about species and higher taxa, and utility services for interpreting names and looking up the identifiers and complete scientific names used for species in the GBIF portal.

Occurrence: Provides access to occurrence information crawled and indexed by GBIF and search services to do real time paged search and asynchronous download services to do large batch downloads.

Maps: Provides simple services to show the maps of GBIF mobilised content on other sites. The site allows for finding and accessing data in an interoperable semantic framework (GBIF taxonomy) for reuse. They even provide an API to discover scientific papers reusing GBIF data.

Figure 8: iNaturalist integrated in GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/es/dataset/50c9509d-22c7-4a22-a47d-8c48425ef4a7>) and one iNaturalist observation integrated as a GBIF occurrence (<https://www.gbif.org/es/occurrence/3455477481>)

1.6 Envidat

[EnviDat](#) is the environmental data portal and repository developed by the Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL. They make environmental monitoring and research data accessible. EnviDat supports the user-friendly registration, documentation, storage, publication, search and retrieval of datasets from the environmental domain in Switzerland.

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EnviDat provides support on managing and publishing research datasets and provides a DOIs. EnviDat is generally open for all types of WSL research data in a range of data formats. The datasets must be: Curated, Quality-controlled, Documented (reusable) and Publication-ready.

Figure 9: EnviDat portal and the view of a dataset reference accessible as a ZIP file

1.7 Environmental indicator catalogue

European and international bodies regularly develop environmental indicators mainly for policy monitoring purposes. However, a large number of them are scattered in all dissemination media, making them difficult to identify and quickly collect. The 'Environmental indicator catalogue' responds to the need for a repository of all available indicators. It is an inventory of almost 200 European indicators, providing a one-stop shop for indicators on environmental and environment-related topics. Currently, the catalogue includes indicators produced mainly by Eurostat and the European Environment Agency (EEA), but also some indicators from the Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) and other international sources.

This is a different catalogue, which does not deal with environmental data but environmental indicators. The data is shared as an excel file that enumerates the indicators and presents links for where to find the indicator as well as the metadata about it. The catalogue is organised according to environmental themes and sub-themes and the indicators are listed under sub-themes. Themes, sub-themes and indicators are all listed in alphabetical order. Next to an indicator's name: its owner and code are mentioned in parentheses. An indicator metadata file provides information on the definition, properties, dissemination and methodology for developing the indicator. The catalogue can be accessed from the search function at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/home>, (see Figure below).

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The screenshot shows the Eurostat website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Eurostat logo and a search bar. Below the navigation bar, there is a search results page for the term 'Environment'. The search bar contains the text 'Environment' and a search button. The results are displayed in a list format. The first result is titled 'Environment' and is dated '1 February 2024'. It includes a brief description: 'Highlights Environment statistics provide information on the environment around us and the mutual relationship between natural resources and human activities. Thus, these statistics give...'. Below the description, there is a 'Browse page' button. The second result is titled 'Environment - functional urban areas' and is dated '25 November 2024'. It includes a 'CODE: urb_fmrv' and an 'UPDATED: 25 November 2024' date. Below the title, there are buttons for 'Access dataset', 'Download data', and 'Show in data tree'. There is also an 'Access metadata' button. At the bottom of the results, there are filters for 'Time frequency: Annual' and 'Urban audit indicator: Multiple (26)'. On the left side of the search results, there is a sidebar with a list of products and their counts, such as 'Data (348)', 'Datasets (275)', 'Thematic sections (73)', 'News (471)', 'News articles (382)', 'Euro indicators (77)', 'Podcasts (12)', 'Publications (1854)', 'Statistical books/Pocketbooks (749)', 'Statistics Explained articles (407)', 'Manuals and guidelines (284)', 'Statistical working papers (172)', 'Leaflets and other brochures (70)', 'Glossary (57)', 'Statistical reports (45)', 'Flagship publications (24)', 'Key Figures (21)', 'Interactive publications (18)', and 'Statistics in Focus (5)'. The 'Environment' filter is selected in the sidebar.

Figure 10: [Search results using 'Environment' as filter](#)

1.8 Global Forest Watch

The Global Forest Watch includes global as well as European coverage, [Global Forest Watch](#) (GFW) Data API (<https://data-api.globalforestwatch.org/>) allows access to the datasets which can be visualized, analyzed, and downloaded. You can find information not only about conservation, but also land use and forest communities.

Data is classified using six categories: Forest Change, Land Use, Conservation, People and Forest Cover.

Figure 11. User interface GFW dataset catalogue

There is the possibility to connect with ArcGIS server in order to create a layer or a story in ArcGIS Online.

You can find more information about how to find and access the different datasets here:

<https://www.globalforestwatch.org/help/developers/guides/discover-datasets-in-the-data-catalog/>

1.9 LifeWatch ERIC

LifeWatch European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) Metadata catalogue <https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/> allow users to retrieve multiple data. This catalogue includes the data of [national nodes](#). LifeWatch is a Research Infrastructure providing access to the world's biodiversity content, services and communities. Its API is available here: <https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/doc/api/index.html>

The catalogue is based on Geonetwork so we can use the OGC CSW API to get the metadata using:

<https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu/srv/eng/csw?request=GetCapabilities&service=CSW>

You can find six kinds of resources: Virtual Research Environment (VREs), datasets, services, workflows and research sites. The documentation of the datasets is based on the Ecological Metadata Language ([EML](#)) v.2.2.0 standard. The other resource metadata is provided as a customization of ISO1939 standard.

Figure 12. User interface LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue filter by datasets.

The metadata includes ontologies and thesauris to facilitate semantic interoperability. In addition, LifeWatch ERIC provides the EcoPortal, a repository of semantic resources for ecology and related domains: <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/>. It includes the eLTER vocabulary and much more. Currently, this portal integrates a tool to perform an ontology FAIRness assessment (<https://github.com/agroportal/fairness>). See more details about the EcoPortal in <https://www.fair-impact.eu/use-cases/improving-ecological-metadata-fairness-through-semantic-services-integration-ecoportal>.

1.10 ICOS data portal

The <https://data.icos-cp.eu/portal/> is the research and access service of the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS). This portal is focused on observational data and elaborated products on greenhouse gases. It includes three levels of data and data products: level 0 is related to raw data; level1 is intermediate observational data; Level 2 is the final quality controlled observational data; and Level 3 that is elaborated products by scientific communities that rely on ICOS data products. Datasets can be visualised and downloaded fully and/or partially.

The data is also findable through a SPARQL endpoint <https://meta.icos-cp.eu/sparqlclient/?type=CSV>. In addition, there are some tools available, <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/tools> that allow visualisation, analyses and management of data, as well as providing support for co-operation in a Virtual Research Environment. Here is the link to find more detail about how to access data: <https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/about-data-portal/how-to-use>.

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Figure 13. User interface ICOS data portal

2. Environmental Datasets

This section lists a selection of datasets, which are linked with the project [use cases](#), found in the catalogues previously mentioned.

Table 1: Datasets linked with project uses cases

Use Cases	Dataset	Catalogue
Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool	Biodiversity (env_biodiv)	EUROSTAT
Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool	GLAD Confidence Footprint	GFW
High resolution SWE in selected mountain regions	Snow water equivalent for reference date April 1 for Wägital catchment, starting 1943	ENVIDAT
Drought Monitoring at high resolution throughout Italy	Soil moisture deficit during the vegetation growing season, annual time-series, 2000-2021, Aug. 2022	EEA
Global drought monitoring at high resolution	Soil moisture data from a Wireless Sensor Network of Sierra Nevada LTER platform	DEIMS

Air quality assessment at continental scale	CAMS European air quality forecasts	CAMS
Air quality assessment at regional scale		
EU reforestation tool	Tree planting occurrences	GBIF
	Biodiversity of the epiphytic lichenic vegetation in the Alentejo Coast (area of Sines)	LifeWatch
Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales	Global ocean low and mid trophic levels biomass content hindcast	CMEMS
Development of the World-reforestation monitor	Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation 2016-present (raster 10 m), Europe, daily	CLMS
Tools and data for improved biomass estimation	Soil Biomass Productivity maps of grasslands and pasture, of croplands and of forest areas in the European Union (EU27)	JRC

Regarding the ICOS catalogue, we didn't find a dataset relevant to the use cases.

3. Measuring the FAIRness of some of the geospatial resources.

Several ways to measure how FAIR data is are emerging, mainly driven by the need to develop data management plans in new projects.

The Data management self-assessment tool: <https://gkhub.earthobservations.org/records/xea2n-tj707> is consists in a questionnaire capturing declarative information for GEO and FAIR Principles. For each Principle, an assessment matrix is proposed addressing the level of compliance and the complementarities / overlap between the FAIR and GEO principles. In contrast the

MQA-Metrics (<https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>) provides a score on the FAIR principles based on checking metadata against various indicators. The Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA) is a tool developed by the consortium of data.europa.eu to study the quality of metadata harvested by data.europa.eu. It is intended to help data providers and data portals to check their metadata quality and to receive suggestions for improvements. The tests done in the metadata are classified in the four aspects of the FAIR principles plus some aspects of contextuality.

We establish a mapping between the DCAT profile and ISO 19115.

Table 2: Mapping between DCAT and ISO 19115

DCAT	ISO
Findable	
dcat:keyword	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > MD_Keyword.keyword
dcat:theme	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.topicCategory
dct:spatial	MD_Keyword
Accessibility	
dcat:accessURL	MD_Metadata.distributionInfo > MD_Distribution.transferOptions > MD_DigitalTransferOptions.onLine > CI_OnlineResource.linkage
dcat:downloadURL	MD_Metadata.distributionInfo > MD_Distribution.transferOptions > MD_DigitalTransferOptions.onLine > CI_OnlineResource.linkage
Interoperability	
dct:format	MD_Metadata > MD_Distribution.distributionFormat > MD_Format.name
dcat:mediaType	MD_Metadata > MD_Distribution.distributionFormat > MD_Format.name
Reusability	
dct:license	MD_Metadata > MD_Indentification.resourceConstraints > MD_Constraints.useLimitations
dct:accessRights	MD_Metadata > MD_Indentification.resourceConstraints > MD_LegalConstraints.accessConstraints

dcat:contactPoint	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.citedResponsibleParty
dct:publisher	MD_Metadata > MD_Distribution.distributor > MD_Distributor.distributorContact
Contextuality	
dct:rights	MD_Metadata > MD_Indentification.resourceConstraints > MD_LegalConstraints.useConstraints
dct:byteSize	MD_Metadata.distributionInfo > MD_Distribution.transferOptions > MD_DigitalTransferOptions.transferSize
dct:issued	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.date
dct:modified	MD_Metadata > MD_DataIdentification.citation > CI_Citation.date

According to this, we consider appropriated the metadata model fields proposed in the deliverable 2.2 to characterise environmental datasets (see ANNEX).

4. STAC catalogues

The OEMC project has selected The Spatio Temporal Assets Catalogue (STAC) as the standard for cataloguing the data produced in the project. While STAC was initially designed for cataloguing long time series for remote sensing products, several extensions allow for other kinds of data to be catalogued. The STAC catalogues provide two views. One is a human readable interface that allows the user to discover assets. The other is based on an API that responds to JSON files. The following list enumerates the three catalogues used in the project. These catalogues offer new cloud optimized data, mainly Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF, Geopackage and Geoparquet.

- IIASA <https://stac.iiasa.ac.at/?language=en>
- OpenGeoHub: <https://stac.openlandmap.org/?language=en>
- In-situ data and raster layers produced by the project (in progress): <https://stac.earthmonitor.org/?language=es>

5. Related tasks and outputs

This deliverable collects the work completed in the first part of Task 2.2: Analysis of FAIR data status and workflows in WP2 – User-driven system design and FAIR workflows of the project Open Earth Monitor.

Report D2.2 (1st version): Status and prospect for European environmental data.

6. Cited references

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ANNEX

This section was mentioned in the deliverable D2.2.

Proposal for a Metadata model to describe environmental datasets

To catalogue environmental datasets, there is a need to define a minimum set of metadata necessary to collect and query the catalogue and to allow for comparison of similar products based on data quality parameters. This is a first draft of the minimum set of metadata fields we should collect for each dataset.

Table 3 Minimum set of metadata to characterise environmental data

Field	Explanation	Example
ID		1, 2, 3 ...
Geographic scope		EU, national, regional or local
Geographic extent	Name of the locality, region, nation of geographic scope	e.g. Catalunya, Schleswig-Holstein, Lower Austria
Dataset name English Dataset name original		EUNIS Biotopes Austria 2018 <i>EUNIS Biotoptypen Österreichs 2018</i>
Short description / Résumé	A short description of of the dataset to get a rough impression; if not available in English to be translated or created by user	Dataset representing EUNIS classes at Level 2 and partly Level 3
Data provider	Name of the data provider and point of contact	Umweltbundesamt / Environment Agency Austria (EAA)
Reference year(s) available	Years of data available	2018
Geometry	Raster/Vector (Point/Line/Polygon)	Raster
Format	Shape, Geopackage, TIFF	TIFF
CRS/EPSG	Coordinate System	ETRS89/LAEA, EPSG 3035
Spatial Resolution/Scale		10 m
Thematic coverage/Essential variable	Keywords	e.g. forest ecosystems; wetlands; agricultural ecosystems...
Temporal extent	Date or interval of dates of the data capture.	2018
Time series available		No
Time series steps	Interval between data releases	unknown - not to be expected

Legal constraints		Freely accessible Full and open Members state/provider data policy Payment required
Licence	Licence applied to the product	Creative Commons Namensnennung 4.0 International
Attribution & use restrictions	Short sentence summarising both provider description and licence	Umweltbundesamt GmbH, CC-BY 4.0
Data URL	URL of the data	https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/en/dataset/1d1a8d2d-cfe8-46ef-aeda-136c88726b5d
Metadata URL	URL of the data	API Link to Metadata https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/api/3/action/package_show?id=1d1a8d2d-cfe8-46ef-aeda-136c88726b5d
Reference/Technical documentation	if available	
Additional Comments	Size	

It may also be useful to have four additional fields to include considerations about the support to the four main FAIR principles:

Table 4: Additional fields to characterise environmental data “FAIRness

Findable	E.g. Persistent Identifiers	There is no guaranty of persistency
Accessible	E.g. Availability of downloading service	Downloading service requires authentication
Interoperable	E.g. Use of internationally recognised vocabularies	National habitat map classifications difficult to map to EUNIS codes
Reusable	E.g. Licences and data quality issues	Licence prevent derivative products